

A LINEAR COMBINATION WITH SMARANDACHE FUNCTION TO OBTAIN THE IDENTITY¹

by

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In this paper we consider a numerical function $i_p: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ (p is an arbitrary prime number) associated with a particular Smarandache Function $S_p: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ such that $(1/p)S_p(a) + i_p(a) = a$.

1. INTRODUCTION. In [7] is defined a numerical function $S: \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, $S(n)$ is the smallest integer such that $S(n)!$ is divisible by n . This function may be extended to all integers by defining $S(-n) = S(n)$.

If a and b are relatively prime then $S(a \cdot b) = \max\{S(a), S(b)\}$, and if $[a, b]$ is the last common multiple of a and b then $S([a, b]) = \max\{S(a), S(b)\}$.

Suppose that $n = p_1^{a_1} p_2^{a_2} \dots p_r^{a_r}$ is the factorization of n into primes. In this case,

$$S(n) = \max\{S(p_i^{a_i} | i = 1, \dots, r)\} \quad (1)$$

Let $a_n(p) = (p^n - 1)/(p - 1)$ and $[p]$ be the generalized numerical scale generated by $(a_n(p))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$:

$$[p]: a_1(p), a_2(p), \dots, a_n(p), \dots$$

By (p) we shall note the standard scale induced by the net $b_n(p) = p^n$:

$$(p): 1, p, p^2, p^3, \dots, p^n, \dots$$

In [2] it is proved that

$$S(p^a) = p \left(a_{[p]} \right)_{[p]} \quad (2)$$

That is the value of $S(p^a)$ is obtained multiplying by p the number obtained writing the exponent a in the generalized scale $[p]$ and "reading" it in the standard scale (p) .

Let us observe that the calculus in the generalized scale $[p]$ is different from the calculus in the standard scale (p) , because

$$a_{n+1}(p) = pa_n(p) + 1 \quad \text{and} \quad b_{n+1}(p) = pb_n(p) \quad (3)$$

We have also

$$a_m(p) \leq a \Leftrightarrow (p^m - 1)/(p - 1) \leq a \Leftrightarrow p^m \leq (p - 1) \cdot a + 1 \Leftrightarrow m \leq \log_p((p - 1) \cdot a + 1)$$

so if

$$a_{[p]} = v_t a_t(p) + v_{t-1} a_{t-1}(p) + \dots + v_1 a_1(p) = \overline{v_t v_{t-1} \dots v_1}_{[p]}$$

is the expression of a in the scale $[p]$ then t is the integer part of $\log_p((p - 1) \cdot a + 1)$

$$t = \left[\log_p((p - 1) \cdot a + 1) \right]$$

and the digit v_t is obtained from $a = v_t a_t(p) + r_{t-1}$.

In [1] it is proved that

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$$S(p^a) = (p-1) \cdot a + \sigma_{[p]}(a) \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_{[p]}(a) = v_1 + v_2 + \dots + v_v$.

A Legendre formula assert that

$$a! = \prod_{\substack{p_i \leq a \\ p_i \text{ prime}}} p_i^{E_{p_i}(a)}$$

where $E_p(a) = \sum_{j \geq 1} \left\lfloor \frac{a}{p^j} \right\rfloor$.

We have also that ([5])

$$E_p(a) = \frac{(a - \sigma_{[p]}(a))}{p-1} \quad (5)$$

and ([1]) $E_p(a) = \left(\left[\frac{a}{p} \right]_{(p)} \right)_{[p]}$.

In [1] is given also the following relation between the function E_p and the Smarandache function

$$S(p^a) = \frac{(p-1)^2}{p} (E_p(a) + a) + \frac{p-1}{p} \sigma_{[p]}(a) + \sigma_{[p]}(a)$$

There exist a great number of problems concerning the Smarandache function. We present some of these problem.

P. Gronas find ([3]) the solution of the diophantine equation $F_S(n) = n$, where $F_S(n) = \sum_{d|n} S(d)$. The solution are $n=9$, $n=16$ or $n=24$, or $n=2p$, where p is a prime number.

T. Yau ([8]) find the triplets which verifies the Fibonacci relationship

$$S(n) = S(n+1) + S(n+2).$$

Checking the first 1200 numbers, he find just two triplets which verifies this relationship: (9,10,11) and (119,120,121). He can't find theoretical proof.

The following conjecture that: "the equation $S(x) = S(x+1)$, has no solution", was not completely solved until now.

2. The Function $i_p(a)$. In this section we shall note $S(p^a) = S_p(a)$. From the Legendre formula it results ([4]) that

$$S_p(a) = p(a - i_p(a)) \text{ with } 0 \leq i_p(a) \leq \left\lfloor \frac{a-1}{p} \right\rfloor. \quad (6)$$

That is we have

$$\frac{1}{p} S_p(a) + i_p(a) = a \quad (7)$$

and so for each function S_p there exists a function i_p such that we have the linear combination (7) to obtain the identity.

In the following we keep out some formulae for the calculus of i_p . We shall obtain a duality relation between i_p and E_p .

$$\text{Let } a_{(p)} = \underline{u_k u_{k-1} \dots u_1 u_0} = u_k p^k + u_{k-1} p^{k-1} + \dots + u_1 p + u_0.$$

Then

$$a = (p-1) \left(u_k \frac{p^k - 1}{p-1} + u_{k-1} \frac{p^{k-1} - 1}{p-1} + \dots + u_1 \frac{p-1}{p-1} \right) + (u_k + u_{k-1} + \dots + u_1) + u_0 =$$

$$(p-1) \left(\left[\frac{a}{p} \right]_{(p)} \right) + \sigma_{(p)}(a) = (p-1) E_{(p)}(a) + \sigma_{(p)}(a) \quad (8)$$

From (4) it results

$$a = \frac{S_p(a) - \sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p-1} \quad (9)$$

From (8) and (9) we deduce

$$(p-1) E_p(a) + \sigma_{(p)}(a) = \frac{S_p(a) - \sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p-1}.$$

So,

$$S_p(a) = (p-1)^2 E_p(a) + (p-1) \sigma_{(p)}(a) + \sigma_{[p]}(a) \quad (10)$$

From (4) and (7) it results

$$i_p(a) = \frac{a - \sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \quad (11)$$

and it is easy to observe a complementary with the equality (5).

Combining (5) and (11) it results

$$i_p(a) = \frac{(p-1) E_p(a) + \sigma_{(p)}(a) - \sigma_{[p]}}{p} \quad (12)$$

From

$$a = \overline{v_t v_{t-1} \dots v_{1|p}} = v_t (p^{t-1} + p^{t-2} + \dots + p + 1) + v_{t-1} (p^{t-2} + p^{t-3} + \dots + p + 1) + \dots + v_2 (p + 1) + v_1$$

it results that

$$a = (v_t p^{t-1} + v_{t-1} p^{t-2} + \dots + v_2 p + v_1) + v_t (p^{t-2} + p^{t-1} + \dots + 1) + v_{t-1} (p^{t-3} + p^{t-4} + \dots + 1) + \dots +$$

$$v_3 (p + 1) + v_2 = \left(a_{[p]} \right)_{(p)} + \left[\frac{a}{p} \right] - \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right]$$

because

$$\left[\frac{a}{p} \right] = \left[v_t (p^{t-2} + p^{t-3} + \dots + p + 1) + \frac{v_t}{p} + v_{t-1} (p^{t-3} + p^{t-4} + \dots + p + 1) + \frac{v_{t-1}}{p} + \dots + \right.$$

$$\left. + v_3 (p + 1) + \frac{v_3}{p} + v_2 + \frac{v_2}{p} + \frac{v_1}{p} \right] = v_t (p^{t-2} + p^{t-3} + \dots + p + 1) +$$

$$+ v_{t-1} (p^{t-3} + p^{t-4} + \dots + p + 1) + \dots + v_3 (p + 1) + v_2 + \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right]$$

we have $[n + x] = n + [x]$.

Then

$$a = \left(a_{[p]} \right)_{(p)} + \left[\frac{a}{p} \right] - \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right] \quad (13)$$

or

$$a = \frac{S_p(a)}{p} + \left[\frac{a}{p} \right] - \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right]$$

It results that

$$S_p(a) = p \left(a - \left(\left[\frac{a}{p} \right] - \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right] \right) \right) \quad (14)$$

From (11) and (14) we obtain

$$i_p(a) = \left[\frac{a}{p} \right] - \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right] \quad (15)$$

It is know that there exists $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that the relation

$$\left[\frac{m-n}{p} \right] = \left[\frac{m}{p} \right] - \left[\frac{n}{p} \right] \quad (16)$$

is not verifies.

But if $\frac{m-n}{p} \in \mathbb{N}$ then the relation (16) is satisfied.

From (11) and (15) it results

$$\left[\frac{a - \sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right] = \left[\frac{a}{p} \right] - \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right].$$

This equality results also by the fact that $i_p(a) \in \mathbb{N}$.

From (2) and (11) or from (13) and (15) it results that

$$i_p(a) = a - (a_{[p]})_{(p)} \quad (17)$$

From the condition on i_p in (6) it results that $\Delta = \left[\frac{a-1}{p} \right] - i_p(a) \geq 0$.

To calculate the difference $\Delta = \left[\frac{a-1}{p} \right] - i_p(a)$ we observe that

$$\Delta = \left[\frac{a-1}{p} \right] - i_p(a) = \left[\frac{a-1}{p} \right] - \left[\frac{a}{p} \right] + \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right] \quad (18)$$

For $a \in [kp+1, kp+p-1]$ we have $\left[\frac{a-1}{p} \right] = \left[\frac{a}{p} \right]$ so

$$\Delta = \left[\frac{a-1}{p} \right] - i_p(a) = \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right] \quad (19)$$

If $a = kp$ then $\left[\frac{a-1}{p} \right] = \left[\frac{kp-1}{p} \right] = \left[k - \frac{1}{p} \right] = k-1$ and $\left[\frac{a}{p} \right] = k$.

So, (18) becomes

$$\Delta = \left[\frac{a-1}{p} \right] - i_p(a) = \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right] - 1 \quad (20)$$

Analogously, if $a = kp+p$, we have

$$\left[\frac{a-1}{p} \right] = \left[\frac{p(k+1)-1}{p} \right] = \left[k+1 - \frac{1}{p} \right] = k \quad \text{and} \quad \left[\frac{a}{p} \right] = k+1$$

so, (18) has the form (20).

For any number a , for which Δ is given by (19) or by (20), we deduce that Δ is maximum when $\sigma_{[p]}(a)$ is maximum, so when

$$a_M = \underbrace{(p-1)(p-1)\dots(p-1)}_{t \text{ terms}} p \quad (21)$$

That is

$$\begin{aligned} a_M &= (p-1)a_1(p) + (p-1)a_{t-1}(p) + \dots + (p-1)a_2(p) + p = \\ &= (p-1) \left(\frac{p^1-1}{p-1} + \frac{p^{t-1}-1}{p-1} + \dots + \frac{p^2-1}{p-1} \right) + p = \\ &= (p^1 + p^{t-1} + \dots + p^2 + p) - (t-1) = pa_t(p) - (t-1) \end{aligned}$$

It results that a_M is not multiple of p if and only if $t-1$ is not a multiple of p .

In this case $\sigma_{[p]}(a) = (t-1)(p-1) + p = pt - t + 1$ and

$$\Delta = \left[\frac{\sigma_{[p]}(a)}{p} \right] = \left[t - \frac{t-1}{p} \right] = t - \left[\frac{t-1}{p} \right].$$

So $i_p(a_M) \geq \left[\frac{a_M-1}{p} \right] - t$ or $i_p(a_M) \in \left[\left[\frac{a_M-1}{p} \right] - t, \left[\frac{a_M-1}{p} \right] \right]$. If $t-1 \in (kp, kp+p)$ then

$$\left[\frac{t-1}{p} \right] = k \text{ and } k(p-1) + 1 < \Delta(a_M) < k(p-1) + p + 1 \text{ so } \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \Delta(a_M) = \infty.$$

We also observe that

$$\left[\frac{a_M-1}{p} \right] = a_t(p) - \left[\frac{t-1}{p} \right] = \frac{p^{t+1}-1}{p-1} - \left[\frac{t-1}{p} \right] \in \left[\frac{p^{kp+1}-1}{p-1} - k, \frac{p^{kp+p+1}-1}{p-1} - k \right].$$

Then if $a_M \rightarrow \infty$ (as p^x), it results that $\Delta(a_M) \rightarrow \infty$ (as x).

$$\text{From } \frac{i_p(a_M)}{\left[\frac{a_M-1}{p} \right]} = \frac{a_t(p) - t}{a_t(p) - \left[\frac{t-2}{p} \right]} \rightarrow 1 \text{ it results } \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{i_p(a)}{[a-1]p} = 1.$$

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